

8th International Workshop on
ON-BOARD PAYLOAD DATA COMPRESSION

28-30 September 2022
Athens - Greece

Joint Super-Resolved Compressive Sensing and Encryption for Earth Observation Applications

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Outline

- Introduction
- **Background on Compressive Sensing (CS)**
- **Review of the SURPRISE instrument**
- **Design of the encryption algorithm**
- **Security evaluation**
- **Overhead complexity evaluation**
- **Conclusions**

Introduction (1)

- Continuous increase in data from Earth Observation (EO) imaging sensors, and high demand for higher resolution
- New units must deal with large data flows, limited energy consumption constraints, data transmission to ground bottleneck
- **Solution:** improved ways of acquiring images, *Compressive Sensing (CS)*
 - CS enables sensing by optical light modulation, followed by image reconstruction at the ground segment
 - Recent reconstruction methods are based on deep learning → significantly improved reconstruction

Introduction (2)

- **SURPRISE** (*SUper-Resolved comPRessive InStrumEnt*):
 - EU-funded project for EO applications in **VNIR and MIR**
 - Will be completed in **Q3 2023**
 - *Goal*: demonstration of a spectral instrument with enhanced spatial resolution, and onboard **encryption** and image processing capabilities
- Randomization of the sensing process makes the SURPRISE image sensing equivalent to a symmetric-key encryption system
 - Strong security properties, at the expense of little additional complexity

The partnership

CNR-IFAC: 'Nello Carrara' Institute of Applied Physics - National Research Council of Italy (IT) – *Lead Partner*

CSEM: Centre Suisse d'electronique et de microtechnique SA - Recherche et Developpement (CH)

POLI-TO: Politecnico Di Torino (IT)

ACRI-ST SAS (FR)

SAITEC SRL (IT)

RESOLVO SRL (IT)

IPMS: Fraunhofer Gesellschaft Zur Foerderung Der Angewandten Forschung E.V. (DE)

LEONARDO SpA (IT)

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CS background

- General CS equation:

$$y = \Phi x$$

- Image x can be **represented as a small set of measurements**, y , via the projection onto a random subspace defined by the *sensing matrix* Φ
- If x is “sparse” in some domain, it can be recovered from y and Φ using suitable **nonlinear algorithms**, e.g. deep learning

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SURPRISE design (1)

SURPRISE design (2)

- **Super-resolved** GEO whiskbroom imager
- The scene is acquired serially, one *macro-pixel* at a time
 - *macro-pixel*: image in the instantaneous field of view
- Each *macro-pixel* is sensed with a single detector and reconstructed into a block of $n \times n$ *micro-pixels*
- n is the so-called *super-resolution factor* as it specifies how many micro-pixels can be reconstructed from measurements
- CS reconstruction algorithm: deep learning method ISTA-Net+
 - non-linear transformation via convolutional operators – learns a sparsification operator for images

SURPRISE design (3)

- Super-resolved scene acquisition

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Encryption algorithm (1)

$$\mathbf{y} = \Phi \mathbf{x}$$

- \mathbf{x} : original signal, Φ : **cryptographic key**, \mathbf{y} : encrypted payload
- Perfect secrecy: \mathbf{y} does not reveal anything about \mathbf{x} , i.e.

$$p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y}) = p(\mathbf{x})$$
$$I(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = 0$$

- **Perfect secrecy:**

1. the sensing matrix Φ has Gaussian i.i.d entries and it is changed at every CS acquisition (**not true for SURPRISE** because of binary masks)
2. the energy of the measurements \mathbf{y} is constant (**also not true...**)

Encryption algorithm (2)

- For random number generation, one can generate a sequence of pseudo-random matrices, one for each image acquisition, via **cryptographically secure pseudo-random bit generators**
- Low-complexity stream cyphers **Salsa-20/ChaCha-20** (sum of values from fixed-size registers, XOR, 1-bit data shift)
- Number of iterations can be modulated
- Rate (x86 arch.): 1 pseudo-random byte with 4 clock cycles
- They work in constant-time regime: great resistance against side channel attacks
- Patent-free

Encryption algorithm (3)

- Attackers can always infer the energy \mathbf{e}_x by observing \mathbf{y}
 - ✓ Corresponds to reconstructing the image without super-resolution
- Hence, we employ energy normalization of \mathbf{y} , encrypt the normalization factor $\mathbf{E}[\mathbf{e}_y]$ with the same stream cypher, and consider it as an additional measurement

- Final encrypted payload:

$$\mathbf{y}_n = \left\{ \mathbf{y} / \sqrt{\mathbf{e}_y}, E[\mathbf{e}_y] \right\}$$

- The increase in the computational overhead does not burden too much the system design

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Security evaluation

- We measure the advantage an attacker might have in attacking SURPRISE with respect to a perfectly secure system
- **Answer this:** Given two images x_1 and x_2 , cyphered signal y , and decoder $D(y)$, has y been obtained from x_1 or x_2 ?
- P_d : prob. of correct decision, P_f : false alarm prob.
- x_1 and x_2 are **θ -distinguishable** when, for every possible $D(y)$:

$$P_d - P_f < \theta \quad (4)$$

Results (1)

- Independent reconstruction is carried out for adjacent macro-pixels (worst-case scenario)
- Even for very small macro-pixels ($n=4$), θ takes very small values ($\theta \simeq 0,01$)

Results (2)

- The complexity of the attack on whole images is comparable to brute-force attacks on the encryption key
- **Example:**
 - Two values for each macro-pixel
 - Original image: 128 x 128 (32×32 macro-pixels, each of 4×4 micro-pixels)
 - Inference prob. *from measurements*: $2^{-51} = 3.5634e^{-300}$
 - Inference prob. *from brute-force guessing a 256-bit key*: $2^{-256} = 8.6362e^{-78}$

Results (3)

Original image

**Reconstruction with the
SURPRISE instrument**

**Reconstruction without
knowledge of the key**

Results (4)

Original image

Reconstruction from the
energy of the measurements

- Measurements \mathbf{y} with length m for each macro-pixel
- Energy of the measurements \mathbf{e}_y
- Super-resolution factor \mathbf{n}
- Estimated energy of the original macro-pixel:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{2m}{n} e_y \quad (5)$$

- Nearest-neighbor interpolation on each macro-pixel from the corresponding estimated energy

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Stream cypher complexity

- Salsa-20/Chacha-20 maps a 256-bit *key*, a 64-bit *nonce* and a 64-bit *counter* onto a 512-bit pseudo-random sequence:
 - 32 sums ($a + b \bmod 2^{32}$)
 - 32 XORs ($a \oplus b$)
 - 32 bit shifts ($a \ll b$)
- Estimated complexity (x86 architecture): 4 to 14 cycles per byte
- **Ex.: $n=4$** , $4 \times 4 = 16$ micro-pixels $\rightarrow 8 \div 28$ cycles for measurement

Energy normalization complexity

- Vector of measurements \mathbf{y} composed of L entries:
 - $2 * L$ multiplications (inner products and divisions by energy norm. factor)
 - $L-1$ sums (sums of the inner products)
 - 1 square root
- Assuming the square root's cost negligible, the overhead is equal to 2 multiplications, 1 sum for measurement
- **Total overhead (stream cypher + energy normalization):**
 - 16 bits per measurement, x86 architecture, $n=4$:
 - $11 \div 32$ cycles for measurement

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Conclusions

- **SURPRISE**: super-spectral instrument for EO applications in the visible and medium infrared range
- **Encryption can be embedded into the sensing/compression process**
- Computationally secure symmetric key encryption system thanks to the Salsa-20/ChaCha-20 pseudo-random bit generators, as proven by theoretical and θ -distinguishability evaluation
- Very little additional overhead required by the employed encryption design